

**THE TRAINING DIMENSION OF SOCIAL WORKERS IN THE STATE
OF TOCANTINS: A REFLECTION BASED ON THE CURRICULUM
GUIDELINES OF THE BRAZILIAN ASSOCIATION OF EDUCATION
AND RESEARCH IN SOCIAL SERVICE (ABEPSS)**

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ABSTRACT

The problematization of work involves the process of professional training of social workers placed in PPC's of Social Service courses of public and private HEIs in the State of Tocantins. The study methodology comprises documentary research, using the five PPC's of public and private HEIs in the State. As a result of the study, some convergences stand out: incorporation of foundations for professional training; promotion of academic research and university extension; in relation to the striking differences, it was identified: fragmentation in the teaching-learning process and in professional training; absence of affirmation of critical social theory in the respective PPC's, among others. It was suggested in the study, an empirical research with the HEIs in order to investigate how the training process of the social worker has been taking place, considering that the referred research was documentary and bibliographical, as well as the feedback of the study with the surveyed HEIs. The collected data will serve as a basis for a critical reflection on the social worker training process and the information will be shared with the CRESS-TO that will serve for future collective discussions of the council, providing a review in the PPC's according to the indications in the study. The information is pertinent to suggest a revision in the PPC's of the HEIs in view of the need for constant articulation with the DC of the ABEPSS of 1996.

Keywords: Ethical Political Project; ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines; Professional qualification; Social service; State of Tocantins.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bearing in mind the socio-political context that the country is experiencing, in times of setbacks and social achievements, advances in conservatism and a discredit on better days for the less favored population, the referred study is articulated with the ABEPSS proposal and goes against the Profession Regulation Law and the 1993 Code of Ethics defended by the CFESS/CFESS set, being made explicit in the profession project with a hegemony that is in line with Marxist social theory, which seeks to articulate in what way the ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines of 1996 reflect on the professional training of graduates and professionals who work in public and social policies.

ABEPSS defends critical education through the essence of the Political Ethical Project and the denial of conservatism and the restriction of individuals' freedom. Answers were sought to our concern about the formative dimension of the Social Worker, having as a starting point the investigation in the PPC's of the Social Service courses of the five (5) HEIs in the state and their connection with the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines.

Because studies on the discussion and implementation of the current Guidelines have already been prepared and published, the research uses such data, which will greatly contribute to the development and strengthening of the profession, highlighting the university as a plural, diverse space with multiple knowledge, it is salutary that the research results are widely disseminated in the academic environment among the collegiate of the courses in order to expand knowledge and discussion among undergraduates, graduates, professors. Therefore, it is up to Social Work to shield itself against the anti-democratic and harmful attacks of capital through its history of struggles and resistance.

During the investigation, no value judgment was used in the PPC's analyses, on the contrary, an attempt was made to indicate relevant aspects of the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines to contribute to the strengthening of the Political Ethical Project and consequently of the profession in Brazil.

Problematizing the study that involves the theme and its delimitation mentioned above at the beginning of this introduction, their primary task is to “investigate the professional training process of social workers placed in PPC's of Social Work courses at public and private HEIs in the state of Tocantins”. It was assumed that the five HEIs in the state of Tocantins underwent some changes in their curricula, such as the legal requirements of MEC (2001) and ABEPSS (1996), in view of the political situation that the country is going through, because at the same

time which follow the course of constant corporate transformations, which indicated the need to investigate how this process occurred and identify the changes.

Regarding the concerns that motivated the study of the subject, it focused on identifying guiding questions capable of reaching satisfactory answers that will contribute to the investigation, among which are: How can one perceive the materialization of the professional training project in the PPC's of the five HEIs in the state of Tocantins? In the analyzed PPC's of the five HEIs, can one perceive a critical attitude of the category towards the market expansion of higher education? Is it possible to perceive in the PPC's of HEIs in the state of Tocantins, the inseparability between the ethical political project of Social Work and the Curriculum Guidelines of ABEPSS?

The study methodology comprises documentary and bibliographical research using the five PPC's of public and private HEIs in the state of Tocantins. The study precedes analysis of the PPC's in the light of the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines, bibliographic review and content analysis. The focus on the ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines of 1996 in relation to the curricular matrices of the Social Service courses in the state of Tocantins, according to the respective PPC's, demonstrated the need for documental research, with a view to contributing to the discussion once resumed on the necessary reformulation of each PPC.

The history of the profession has been portrayed over the years by social workers who have experienced the historical trajectory of struggles and achievements of the category. The celebration of the 80th anniversary of the profession in Brazil was remembered through various manifestations promoted by the CFESS/CRESS group through scientific production, debates, meetings, seminars, exhibition of works on the path of the profession to the present day.

Duriguetto and Marro (2018), reaffirm the process of mobilization of the profession and its direct relationship with social movements in favor of the realization and conquest of social rights.

The approximation of Social Work with the struggles, organizations and social movements that defend the rights, interests and societal projects of the subaltern classes dates from the beginning of the 1960s with the Latin American Reconceptualization Movement. The condition for this first approximation was the formation and political action of workers' movements and organizations that developed in the midst of the international context of a preventive counterrevolution of capital that had sharp repercussions on the continent. It is in this context of social effervescence that segments of the forefront of the category begin to rethink the function of the profession in the face of social contradictions and tune in to the universe of struggles and demands of workers, acting towards undermining the traditional bases of the profession in the its theoretical-methodological, organizational and interventional dimension. (DURIGUETTO; MARRA, 2018, p. 94-95)

The debate on the professional formation of the Social Worker in the 80 years of institutionalization of the profession in Brazil has been the motto of the approaches of the set CFESS/CRESS and ABEPSS over the years, the constant discussions of the mentioned entities seek to propitiate the emphasis in the indissociability between professional training and the profession project, in this regard we make some contributions.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Revisiting and reflecting on the ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines

The study involves the analysis of the 05 (five) HEIs in the state of Tocantins, bringing to light on-site public courses (state and federal) and private courses (on-site - modular, blended and distance), described in Chart 1. The initial proposal is to deepen the theoretical knowledge about the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines with a focus on the PPC's of the Social Service course, based on the principle of professional hegemony, which is guided by dialectical historical materialism.

This item of fundamental importance brings some reflections relevant to the object of research on screen, that is, the process of professional training of social workers in the state of Tocantins through PPC's of HEIs. With the objective of answering the questions raised in the introduction of the work regarding the convergences and/or divergences in the PPC's of the Social Service courses of the five HEIs in the state of Tocantins, two comparative tables are presented below for further reflection . The methodology used was very dynamic, seeking to address the most exciting topics that directly concern the professional training of Social Workers.

It is made aware that, due to the alteration of some PPC's, an attempt was made to readjust the data in line with the reflections initiated previously in order to avoid misunderstandings, which is understandable since we are dealing with the dynamicity of the facts and, of these with our research object. It should be noted that the data shown in the two tables are apprehensions of the analyzes contained in each document of the respective HEIs.

2.2 Table 1: Demonstration of the main characteristics of the Social Work course at HEIs

HEI	CREATION	TYPE	MODALITY	CH	CH INTERNSHIP	WITHOUT.	ACTIV. COMPLETE
ITOP	2013	Toilet	In person	2,448 hours	450h	8	120h
UNOPAR	2017	Toilet	EaD / Blended	3,020h	450h	8	150h
UFT	2007.2	public	In person	3,255h	540h	9	135h
UNIP	2018	Toilet	In person	3,600 hours (3,000 hours)	450h	8	150h
			EaD and Flex	3,040 hours			
UNITINS	2016	public	In person	2,400h	450h	8	150h

The intention in exposing the data of the five HEIs was not to make any value judgments about the dynamics of the academic activities of each institution, but rather to make each HEI that offers the Social Work course in the state of Tocantins in evidence, seeking to know the pedagogical proposal and the convergences and divergences found during the documentary research. From the results obtained, the investigation followed its natural course by scrutinizing every detail that diverged or converged with the 1996 ABEPSS DC, with the document prepared by the Social Service Specialist Commission (1999) and with the CFESS/CRESS set. Social Work defends training guided by critical social theory capable of understanding the movement of reality, in view of the constant societal transformations that we are subject to.

Below, Table 2 describes some requirements that are deemed essential for further reflection.

2.3 TABLE 2- HEI axes and indicators according to the 1996 DC.

Analysis Axes	Indicators	HEI
1. PROFESSIONAL TRAINING FUNDAMENTAL CORE	1. Adoption of a critical social theory that allows the apprehension of the social totality.	UFT ⁷ ITOP, UNITINS
	2. Presence of interdisciplinarity in the professional training project.	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS, UNOPAR, UNIP
	3. Understanding of ethics as a principle that permeates all professional training.	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS

⁷It is reiterated that the Social Service course at UFT is in the process of approving its new PPC for 2019-2020 (2021).

	4. Complies with the Vocational Training Foundation Cores	UFT, UNITINS, ITOP
	5. The meaning of Social Work in its contradictory nature, expressed in the confrontation of classes in force in society and present in institutions, which also refers to the understanding of organizational and institutional dynamics in the state and private spheres.	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS
	6. The different political projects existing in Brazilian society: their foundations, principles, analysis of society, strategies and programs.	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS
	7. Theoretical-methodological, technical-operative and ethical-political competence are fundamental requirements that allow professionals to face the situations they are faced with, clearly envisioning corporate projects, their class ties, and their own work process .	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS
	8. Historical, theoretical and methodological foundations are necessary to understand the cultural formation of professional work and, in particular, the ways of thinking of social workers.	UFT, ITOP, UNITINS
2. NEW LOGIC CURRICULUM AD 1996	1. Adequacy to the DC of ABEPSS 1996.	UFT
	2. DC 2002 of the MEC.	ITOP, UNITINS

As shown in Table 2, the HEIs are consistent with regard to the requirements of “Professional Training”, demonstrating a commitment to the quality of teaching guided by the Ethical Political Project of the category. In relation to the category Rationale Nuclei of Vocational Training, the PPC of the respective HEIs: UFT and UNITINS are articulated with the requirements of the DC of ABEPSS of 1996. The ITOP faculty presents in its PPC the requirements of the DC of 2002, as highlighted in table 2; “Adoption of a critical social theory that enables the apprehension of the social totality; presence of interdisciplinarity in the professional training project; understanding of ethics as a principle that permeates all professional training; necessary inseparability between academic and professional supervision in the internship activity”. Such requirements are essential for critical training guided by social theory, hegemonically recognized by the CFESS/CRESS set since the rupture of Social Work with conservatism.

As seen, it is observed that only the 3 HEIs: *UFT, ITOP and UNITINS* sought cohesion and articulation with the assumptions indicated by ABEPSS (1996) in relation to the Nuclei of Fundamentals of Vocational Training, whether they are: Nucleus of Theoretical-Methodologies of Social Life; Nucleus of Fundamentals of Socio-Historical Formation of the Brazilian Society and the Nucleus of Fundamentals of Professional Work.

In the speeches, it should be observed if there is theoretical consistency and fruitful analysis of the conjuncture of the narrated facts, pluralism must be evidenced in the disciplines, in the research and in the extension. The articulation and indissociability between the political project and the professional training of the Social Worker is that the DC of ABEPSS of 1996 are consolidated anchored by the commitment to a critical formation guided by dialectical historical materialism. For (FORTUNA and GUEDES, 2020, p. 25):

Professional training, as well as the production of knowledge in social work, must go beyond the empty theoretical perspective of a concrete base and also the mechanical use of techniques, the strictly operational dimension and actually understand who are the social subjects for whom the professional action turns and what are the conditions that are objectified in their daily life given the historical conditions experienced. It is in this direction that the contents necessary for the professional training of social workers, according to the Curriculum Guidelines for Social Service courses (ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO E PESQUISA EM SERVIÇO SOCIAL, 1996), refer us to the set of knowledge organized into three core foundations, intrinsically, linked: theoretical-methodological aspects of social life; particularity of the socio-historical formation of Brazilian society and fundamentals of professional work [..].

As they reaffirm, the 1996 ABEPSS Vocational Training Rationale Centers should be parameters for the production of professional knowledge, representing a historical milestone for Social Work. It can be seen from the documents analyzed in the HEIs: *UNIP and UNOPAR*, that this articulation with the DC is biased, ~~from~~ detached from the totality, representing an imminent risk of returning to pragmatism.

For Fortuna and Guedes (2020), it is only possible to capture socio-historical determinations from the mediation category. Such ability can lead to the demands posed in the Social Worker's professional routine based on objective, concrete actions and not just on the subjectivity of the subject. They are actions mediated by professional intervention, endowed with knowledge forged by the concentricity of dialectical historical materialism, which will lead the professional posture beyond its intentionality.

Continuing on, we have the axis of the New Curriculum Logic of the 1996 SC, the Skills and Skills that concern the professional's attitude towards institutional demands, which need to be more emphasized in the PPC's analyzed from the two HEIs already mentioned (UNIP and UNOPAR) as the DC of 1996, evidencing the social and political direction of the category are the HEIs: ITOP, UNOPAR and UNITINS that have convergences in relation to the workload of the "Compulsory Curricular Internship and Academic Supervision".

After exposing the points considered convergent by the HEIs, the divergences identified during the analysis of the documents are presented below:

- Absence of the Internship Policy as a requirement of the professional training process guided by critical social theory;
- Absence of articulation with the Ethical Political Project of the category in view of the emphasis on distance learning. There is no exchange of knowledge between student and teacher, the focus of academic guidance is individual;

In both HEIs: UNOPAR and UNIP, the Internship is not “supervised” since there is no record or mention that there is a requirement for systematic supervision of the internship in Social Work according to the 2010 ABEPSS National Internship Policy. of UNOPAR it is only described that the institution has the “Term of Commitment” to be used in the curricular internship, but it does not mention the other documentation necessary for the student’s insertion process.

It is in the exercise of the Supervised Internship, in the relationship between the intern, the institution and the users that it is possible to objectify the essence of a political and critical formation that is concerned with the advance of neoliberalism, which fights hard against the dismantling of historically constructed and conquered social rights, against a market-oriented and lightened formation without due care to reflect the dialectic that involves the subjects.

It is through the production of knowledge that the profession must demonstrate its position in favor of the professional project, expanding the previously academic and pragmatic field of vision, through the teleological capacity anchored by the Marxist perspective. In this way, the professional praxis exercised in the internship field by the supervisor must demonstrate his/her ethical and political commitment to the profession project defended by ABEPSS. The Supervised Internship presupposes more than an exchange between student and teacher, between intern and supervisor, it is the exercise of professional ethics, respect and commitment of both with the subjects' demands . Therefore, this internship and supervision process cannot be lightened and uncritical, detached from the political situation.

According to the document entitled: “ Quality Standards for Authorization and Recognition of Undergraduate Courses in Social Work, ⁸” it is concluded that of the five HEIs surveyed, at least two UNIP and UNOPAR do not present in the researched and publicized documents the following requirements elaborated by the Commission of Specialists of Social Work (1997):

⁸Document prepared by: Maria Marieta dos Santos Koike (UFPE - ABESS) Maria Rachel Tolosa Jorge (UNESP) Mariangela Belfiore Wanderley (PUCSP) Marilda Villela Iamamoto (UFRJ) Marina Maciel Abreu (UFMA).

Higher Education Institutions must present the following data: • reasons and objectives of the course • professional profile • summary and respective bibliography; • curriculum: disciplines per semester/year; course load of subjects and list of professors responsible for subjects; • supervised internship policy and conditions; • criteria and forms of evaluation of teaching/learning; • norms for the elaboration, orientation and evaluation of the TCC - Course Completion Work; • complementary pedagogical activities: monitoring, scientific initiation, extension and others; • research and extension policies: links with teaching. Interdisciplinary dimension of the projects, scope and relationship with the demands of society. (ABEPSS, 1997, p.6-7).

This finding is worrying, while at the same time reinforcing the research presented in the study by Pereira (2010) on the precariousness and expansion of higher education in the EaD modality. The commodified and streamlined logic of distance learning contradicts itself with regard to the principles of the Ethical Political Project of Social Work, which ensures the commitment to quality, critical education, capable of fostering teaching, research and extension as university tripods, a reality that materializes in face-to-face teaching.

2.4 The methodological construction of the research

In view of the methodological procedures, the starting point is the use of the ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines of 1996 and the Pedagogical Projects of the Social Service Courses (PPC's) of the public and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the state of Tocantins. A priori, we seek to identify in these official documents, coherence in relation to the legal assumptions of the Ethical Political Project of the profession, its construction and reassessment in accordance with the legal protections of the CFESS/CRESS set. To give consistency to our investigation and theoretical rigor, it was salutary to understand the dialectical historical method which is considered capable of responding to the demands put under discussion.

[...] The necessary recurrence to the dialectical method, proper to the movement of reality, is not arbitrary. It is an attitude adopted by the researcher who is sensitive to the need to capture reality in its movement, through the contradictions that make it dynamic in a perspective of totality, which does not mean wanting to account for everything, but to discern between the essential, the predominant factor, and the accessory, the secondary elements (GUERRA, 2016, p. 5-6).

As pointed out by Guerra (2016), the researcher needs to question the reasons why he/she is researching that/this object, what is the social relevance of the research for the user population and, above all, which method of analysis will be used. These are triggering questions that need to be resolved, so that you can approach the necessary totality. In order to be

successful in this research, we focused on the search for studies, theses, dissertations and other sources of research that did not indicate a traced path, but not an unfinished one.

The studies began with Revista Temporalis n° 14, year VII from July to December 2007, which highlights as its central theme: “ *Curriculum Guidelines for the Social Service course: on the implementation process.*” Revista Temporalis is published every six months by ABEPSS and had a strong influence on the study and on the results obtained as a theoretical basis. The first three articles deal with the subject of our investigation and resulted in rich knowledge and unveiling of the reality to be researched, as it is a macro study that was carried out in 2006 by ABEPSS. In the period between the field research of the Brazilian Association of Teaching and Research in Social Service (ABEPSS), the country was suffering the consequences of the neoliberal adjustment policy and the education policy was also strongly affected.

From a wide discussion of the category on the construction process of the Curriculum Guidelines and their implementation, the widely known document “Minimum Curriculum for Social Service Courses” approved in 1996 was born ⁹. However, the proposal submitted by ABEPSS to the National Council of Education, which was framed only in 1999, however, the original proposal underwent changes in the approval process in 2001, thus demonstrating such dissatisfaction with the category of Social Workers.

This arduous process, which implied significant losses for the profession and demonstrated the government's disregard for a serious and committed ABEPSS proposal, in the frustrated attempt to overcome the market expansion of higher education institutions in Brazil that did not have criteria regulated by ABEPSS, by the commitment to the quality and responsibility of the teaching given to future and future professionals. In this way, the reflective reading of this journal portrays the trajectory of Social Work's struggle to establish its critical theoretical-methodological and ethical-political bases as an affirmation of the choice for a training marked by the defense of the working class, by the commitment to a decommodified and guided education access to the population living in less favored conditions, through the ethical commitment of professionals who work directly with higher education, social movements, popular education in the dissemination of a culture free of values and social discrimination based on class and belonging.

To subsidize the choice of research method, the discussion is based on the ideas of Kosik (1976), which justifies the essentiality of the method, comprising its entirety.

⁹ABEPSS data recorded in the presentation of Revista Temporalis n° 14.

For Kosik (1976), the discussion of the totality category in classical German philosophy was designed to distinguish the controversial concepts of dialectics and metaphysics. Kosik (1976) refutes the idea that the understanding of the evolutionary processes of reality can be understood only by phenomenal, causal manifestations. However, he considers that: “[...] from the point of view of totality, one understands the dialectic of the law and the causality of phenomena, of the internal essence and of the phenomenal aspects of reality, of the parts and the whole, of the product and of reproduction and so on [...]” (KOSIK, 1976, p.33). As stated by the author, Marx also corroborated this concept, but under a new perspective he built the materialist dialectic.

It is necessary that the researcher understands the path taken by the category of totality, so that he does not make mistaken, empty and unilateral readings of the concept, which has become quite commonplace in academic research. The use of the concept has become commonplace among academics and professionals who subdue a deep knowledge of the totality category without a precise and fruitful reading. It is on this uncritical use that Kosik draws our attention when discussing the risks of submitting to “[...] a *methodological requirement* and a methodological rule of investigation. ” (KOSIK,1976, p. 34). In his approach to materialist philosophy, Kosik urges us to question reality not just as an obligatory requirement, a habitual, pragmatic routine, but based on guiding questions such as: “what is reality? ” (KOSIK, 1976, p. 34). Scrutinizing our capacity a little more, we see that it is necessary to leave our comfort zone, the academic self-indulgence that is presented and, which is accepted without much argument, a detached concept of a concrete reality that seems to expand among professionals, researchers and other scholars.

From these successions, we have a starting point to instigate us not to be mere reproducers of information, of conceptual approaches, but to assume our role as subjects participating in a process under construction, which metamorphoses and needs to be revealed with concreteness. Kosik (1976) warns not to reproduce discourses on the concepts of *totality* from the accumulation of all facts, which is a mistake. From the point of view that this understanding is not possible rationally, it would be to deny history and without history, there is no subject, there is no dialectical movement. (KOSIK, 1976, p.35)

It is considered that the study cannot be started without such approaches on the conception of the category of totality and concreteness to give a solid basis to the work, therefore, O The objective with academic research is to avoid such common mistakes in academia, which tend to leave us with the erroneously disseminated idea about a reality that does not consider societal transformations as a product of social relations and ends up reducing professional work. The constant argumentation of what is set must be questioned, instigated,

refuted, in short, one must not accept a reality as it is presented, without taking into account the contradictions.

3. CONCLUSION

In view of what has been exposed and in the analysis of the respective PPC's, to state that the referred HEIs materialize or not the Ethical Political Project of Social Work just by citing it in their legal documents, would be an assertion without sufficient foundation. It is in subjectivity and professional intentionality that such a statement could be said. However, we can say that the HEIs mentioned in the aforementioned analyses, which did not present legal contributions, which did not make any public document available and did not mention them in their PPC, are the ones closest to denying the materialization of the essence of the Ethical Political Project and not consistent with the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines.

Therefore, it is understood and believed that this study permeated, through the PPC's of the HEIs, a course of the trajectory of the professional training process of social workers in the state of Tocantins, bringing to light some convergent and divergent aspects. Thus, it reiterates the importance of Social Workers to remain in cohesion in the face of capital onslaughts, seeking intellectual and critical maturity through category discussions, dense readings, unconditional support from the CFESSS/CRESS set, among others.

As it is the research's locus, some considerations of distance learning in the state of Tocantins were sought, which subsidized the investigation.

As already highlighted, the presence of the private sector in Brazilian higher education is not new, however the Distance Learning modality (EaD) constitutes an innovative feature of the expansion of the private sector in education. This modality provides a rapid expansion of enrollments and has become highly profitable for the private sector, with Social Work being one of the higher education courses most offered by this modality. Through technological advances in telecommunications, it fosters the growth of transnational private investments, being a promising slice for the market. It is in this context that the first Social Service course in the Distance Learning modality was created in Brazil in 2006, which was pioneered in Tocantins. Offered by a state university (University of Tocantins - Unitins) in partnership with Edcon. (BURGINSKI, SANTOS, RODRIGUES, 2020, p. 400).

As pointed out by the authors, the expansion of EaD courses in Brazil is strengthened in the state of Tocantins with the growth of the private sector and capitalist expansion.

[...] The region that covers the state of Tocantins is located in the territory of geographic transition between the Cerrado and the Amazon Forest, being one

of the territories in which the agricultural frontier expands exponentially, through the hegemonic model of agricultural development , agribusiness [...] (BURGINSK, SANTOS, RODRIGUES, 2020, p. 398).

It is not possible to conclude this work without highlighting this very important data about the capitalist expansion in Tocantins, considering that it is geographically the reference for the investigation. In this respect, there are the pertinent reflections of the authors,

The offer of distance learning higher education courses in Tocantins with payment of monthly fees, with emphasis on Social Work, had a strong popular appeal, as well as being the course with the highest number of enrollments and vacancies available. A territory with the magnitude of Tocantins needs Social Work, therefore, the strategy was to “produce” social workers in mass, with limited training and not in tune with the Curriculum Guidelines. Given the socio-historical conditions of abandonment of this territory, the idea of bringing higher education and socioeconomic development to thousands of people in faraway regions was strongly articulated with the dream of democratizing higher education through a new market, serving the interests of profits. private, through commodified education that does not guarantee quality in professional training. (BURGINSKI SANTOS, RODRIGUES, 2020, p.403-404)

The Social Service course arrived in Tocantins through the Lutheran University of Brazil (ULBRA) which was installed in the capital in 1990. However, the Social Service course in the face-to-face modality was only authorized to operate in 2000. The MEC recognition process only occurred in 2008 (BUSRGISNKI, SANTOS, RODRIGUES, 2020). This institution was not investigated because it no longer offers the Social Work course, however, as it was the first institution to offer the Social Work course in Tocantins, a brief summary of its institutionalization will be made.

In relation to stating whether or not higher education institutions have a critical stance, it is not possible to be sure, as this is a documentary research, it becomes quite subjective to enter a space in which there was no opportunity to experience life's experiences academic, dialogues, among other relevant aspects to issue any position. Regarding the professional posture, there is the statement,

The PEP, so named in the 1990s, is the mature expression of the consolidation of the social direction of the profession in the 1980s, which was established in the process of boiling the class struggle in the country where professionals were organically linked to the working class. Therefore, the political conditions of constitution of the PEP of the Brazilian Social Service must be evaluated considering the following determinants: the fight against the dictatorship, the collage to the social movements of the 1980s, the change of the professional public composed of the middle and impoverished layers, and how the professional and academic vanguards of the category are vanguards of political and social militancy. (ABRAMIDES, 2016, p.471).

The professional skills listed in the DC for Social Service courses (1996) relate to a professional profile capable of understanding the movement of social reality through criticality. In view of the analyzes carried out through the categories identified in Table 2, there are some considerations. Regarding the “Nucleus of Fundamentals of Vocational Training”, the indicators indicate that only the HEIs: ITOP, UFT and UNITINS, were able to meet these requirements.

Observing the axis on the “New Curricular Logic of the 1996 SC”, the HEI UFT and UNITINS sought to meet the requirements set forth by ABEPSS. The ITOP faculty did not make reference to the DC of ABEPSS of 1996, but the DC of 2002, which is why we made such a consideration, since the DC of 2002 have divergences in relation to the proposal of the set CFESS/CRESS and ABEPSS of 1996. However, in relation to the fulfillment of Complementary Activities, all 5 HEIs maintain cohesion in relation to the provisions of the DC of ABEPSS of 1996. On the axis of the “Curricular Internship and Academic Supervision” the HEIs: UFT, UNITINS and ITOP have Regulations and Policy of Internship, carry out systematic internship supervision both in the field and in the classroom. The respective HEIs: UNIP and UNOPAR, do not describe in their PPC's, the necessary documentation for the insertion of the student in the internship field, thus making it difficult to focus more in tune with the requirements of PNE/2010.

HEI UNIP and UNOPAR were not referenced in the axes of analysis because they did not meet the requirements set forth in the 1996 ABEPSS DC. fragmentation of teaching, in the fragility of the contents exposed in the discipline offer, in short, directly reflects on the academic and professional formation. If there is no direction to follow, any one will do. This seems to be the common sense discourse that prevails when it comes to teaching quality, regardless of the social and political direction to which the course is linked.

Specifically in Social Work, these changes tend to limit professional practice to a merely technical nature, as Iamamoto (2014) elucidates:[...]“The discourse that underlies competence-based training can find a favorable setting in the professional culture of Social Work to its diffusion as a result of its links with empiricism and a certain mythification of 'professional practice[...]” (QUEIROZ, 2020, p.55-56 Apud IAMAMOTO, 2014, p.627).

Professional practice must strip itself of fetishes, adjustment behaviors and value judgments, allowing the professional to have freedom and autonomy to intervene in the face of the ills that are presented to him. It is not stated here that the Social Worker fails to meet the institutional demands that are imposed on him, but that he must critically reflect on such

situations, always seeking to be guided by dialogue and respect, taking care to ensure that the subjects have their rights preserved and enforced.

In this regard, the speech of Albiero and Costa (2020, p.70) is reported.

Therefore, it is up to those who maintain a distance from the professional collectivity to break with common sense, with an apparent reality, the result of the alienation caused by capitalism that objectifies people and, in this way, maintains its heritage. It is time to resist so as not to succumb to a series of cowardly, unfair and harmful attacks by the current government. Social Workers must always be ready to fight, to fight. If we have come this far as a profession forged by professional protagonism, we have an ethical commitment to maintain the course of history, to make sure that we are not fighting for utopia.

Between 1994 and 1996, there were several collective moments involving the academic community and the entire professional category in a broad and democratic debate on the Curriculum Guidelines. According to the ABESS/CEDEPSS document from 1996, there were: 200 local workshops, in 67 academic training units affiliated to ABESS, 25 regional workshops and 02 national ones. The professional intention defended by Guerra and other scholars linked to Social Work must permeate professional actions through the dimensions already mentioned: [...] technical-instrumental, theoretical-intellectual, ethical-political and formative (Guerra, 1997, p. .12) [...]"

Finally, it is believed that it is possible to visualize the indissociability between the Political Ethical Project and the 1996 ABEPSS Curriculum Guidelines in the respective PPC's of 3 HEIs, two public and one private. The others fell short of what was expected in relation to the analytical categories: Nucleus of Basis for Professional Training, Supervised Internship and Academic Supervision and New Curriculum Logic of 1996, which were identified during the documentary research in the respective PPC's. In this regard, the speech of Albiero and Costa (2020, p.70) is reported.

Therefore, it is up to those who maintain a distance from the professional collectivity to break with common sense, with an apparent reality, the result of the alienation caused by capitalism that objectifies people and, in this way, maintains its heritage. It is time to resist so as not to succumb to a series of cowardly, unfair and harmful attacks by the current government. Social Workers must always be ready to fight, to fight. If we have come this far as a profession forged by professional protagonism, we have an ethical commitment to maintain the course of history, to make sure that we are not fighting for utopia.

The research provided a unique opportunity to go through each PPC and its curricular matrix, to know the teaching dynamics of the institutions, dialoguing paragraph by paragraph

with the 1996 ABEPSS DC, with the recommendations of the 1999 Commission of Social Service Specialists.

Given the above, it is concluded that the main convergences are: incorporation of core foundations of professional training; promotion of academic research and university extension; systematic supervision in relation to the internship and supervision; focus on teacher qualification (ITOP, UFT and UNITINS); compliance with the workload of the curricular internship; cohesion in relation to compliance with the workload of Complementary Activities: ITOP, UFT, UNIP, UNITINS and UNOPAR.

Regarding the marked divergences, fragmentation in the teaching-learning process and professional training was identified; lack of assertion of critical social theory in the respective PPC's; no description of lines and research groups and university extension projects published on the courses page and on the PPC's (UNIP, UNOPAR); mention of the DC of MEC/2002 in the analyzed documents: (ITOP, UNITINS).

In this way, it is suggested for this study that an empirical research be carried out in HEIs with a view to investigating how the training process of the social worker has been taking place, considering that the aforementioned research was documentary and did not allow such seizures. That the study be returned to the researched HEIs, demonstrating commitment to the academic community. It is believed that the collected data will serve as a basis for a critical reflection on the social worker training process. Share the information with the CRESS-TO Professional Training Commission so that the data presented can serve for future collective discussions of the category.

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